

IDENTIFYING PREFERENCES IN USING N-LIST E-RESOURCES BY THE USERS OF SELECT DEGREE COLLEGES AFFILIATED TO PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH

Ms. Shivani Kaushal

Research Scholar ,

Department of Library & Information Science,
Panjab University, Chandigarh

&

Librarian, GGSDS College, Kheri Gurna (Banur),
A sister Institute of GGSDS College, Chandigarh.

Email: shivanijalota@gmail.com

Dr. Rupak Chakravarty,

Associate Professor,

Department of Library & Information Science,
Panjab University, Chandigarh.

Email: rupak@pu.ac.in

Abstract: This research paper explains the preferences of the N-LIST E-resources among the student and faculty members of the various select Degree Colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. A questionnaire method was used as a tool for collection of data from the 32 select degree colleges in Punjab and Chandigarh. The total data was collected from the 466 out of 513 respondents. The total response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466 respondents, total 286 are users (faculty and student) respondents and 180 are non-users (faculty and student) respondents. The statistical test have been applied and the inferences have been drawn thereof.

Keywords: E-Books, E-Journals, Bibliographical Databases, N-LIST, INFLIBNET, Usage of E-Resources, Degree Colleges of Panjab University, Consortia

1.0 Introduction

With the advent of resource sharing, the Library Consortia have brought economy, efficiency and equality in information availability and its usage. Through Library Consortia, the gap between information resource-rich libraries and resource-deficient libraries is expected to be bridged. Although, there are many consortia in India like UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortia, INDEST Consortia, CSIR Consortia etc which have already gained the popularity in India. Yet, N-LIST is one of such consortia which helps to bridge this gap and provides access to the E-resources to its users.

2.0 N-LIST: An Initiative of NMEICT

The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT) was launched on 3rd Feb, 2009. It initiated a project called “National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)”, popularly known as N-LIST which was formally launched by Shri Kapil Sibal, Union Minister for Human Resource Development, on 4th May, 2010. The N-LIST Project is being jointly executed by the (University Grants Commission- Information Network) UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi. The project provides the cross-subscription to e-resources subscribed by the two Consortia, i.e. subscription to INDEST-AICTE resources for universities and UGC-INFONET resources for technical institutions; and the access to selected e-resources to colleges.

The Faculty and the students from the colleges covered under section 12B/ 2F of UGC Act are eligible to access e-resources through the N-LIST project. These colleges are required to register themselves on the N-LIST Website. During the last three years, the collection has increased from 2,100 to 6,000 e-journals and from 51,000 to 1, 00,000 e-books (ref. 2 homepage), subscribed under the N-LIST Project.

3.0 Review of Literature

Akinola (2009) obtained the results from her study which revealed that majority of the respondents (35.4%) from the University of Ibadan sought information to update knowledge. It was also found that the respondents also sought information for writing of papers or books, reading, and for preparing class lectures. The study on Information seeking behaviour of Social Science Faculty was done by **Chattwal (2014)** which indicates the pen-drive is most preferred as an external storage device due to its large storage capacity as well as convenience of usage was found to be the most preferred by 50.20% participants database appears to be the most suitable usage pattern for the University faculty members. Present study indicates that the main reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources are due to ‘lack of awareness’ by student non-users respondents. A similar study by **Nikam & Pramodini (2007)** indicates that reasons of non-use of UGC-INFONET resources by the Faculty Members and research scholars was 59.50% of respondents attributed the reason as lack of training/ orientation. The other reason included 28.50% of respondents attributed the reasons as ‘lack of awareness’ whereas 10.50% opted ‘Aware but internet connection is not proper’. The authors concluded that the use was marginal and the scientist in the Mysore University Campus need constant guidance and training to maximise the use of UGC-INFONET e-resources. The similar study by **Bhardwaj & Walia (2012)** analyse the rating of the quality of the Electronic Resources in the St. Stephens College library, where majority of the respondents (52.8%) agreed that the ‘Quality of the N-LIST e-resources are excellent’ while 39.68% of the respondents rated the quality of the N-LIST e-resources were good. The authors also concluded that most of the respondents rated N-LIST e-resources very good. The similar study by **Chikkanmanju and Kumbar (2015)** identified the level of satisfaction of student respondents about the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources of the Tumkur University. The study reveals that 46.86% opined that the aided college students are extremely satisfied with the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources.

4.0 Objectives of the Study

- The present study is an attempt to find out the accessibility of N-LIST E-resources and the usage trends used by the faculty and students of the Panjab University, Chandigarh.
- The study was conducted with the following objectives:-
- To analyze and compare the preferences and purpose of using the N-LIST E-resources amongst the faculty and student users in the select Degree Colleges of Panjab University, Chandigarh.

5.0 Methodology and Scope of the Study

A Survey method has been implemented to meet the objectives of the study. The author has collected the data through questionnaire method from the select Degree Colleges which are affiliated to Panjab University. The data have been collected from the 144 faculty users and 142 student users. In 144 faculty users, 114 are males and 30 are females whereas 142 student users, 33 are males and 109 are females. The statistical T-test has been applied to approve the null or alternate hypothesis. This method facilitates yearly accumulation of information from the member colleges in various settings under parameters relevant to the study.

6.0 Scope and Locale of the Study

This study is confined to 18 member colleges. These member colleges are located in Punjab and Chandigarh and are affiliated to Panjab University only.

7.0 Time Period of the Study

The time period of the study will be from Jan 2010 to May 2015.

8.0 (A) Preference Using N-LIST E-resources by Faculty

Table-1: Faculty (Preference Using E-resources)

Sr. No.	Frequency/ Preferences	Always	Frequently	Sometimes	Seldom	Never	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Prefer Print Resource over E-resources	16 (11.11%)	34 (23.61%)	60 (41.67%)	34 (23.61%)	0 (0.00%)	144 (100.00%)
2.	Prefer E-books over E journals	0 (0.00%)	25 (17.36%)	116 (80.56%)	3 (2.08%)	0 (0.00%)	144 (100.00%)

3.	Prefer E-journals over E-books	10 (6.94%)	60 (41.67%)	66 (45.83%)	5 (3.48%)	3 (2.08%)	144 (100.00%)
4.	No search Preference	0 (0.00%)	13 (9.03%)	86 (59.72%)	3 (2.08%)	42 (29.17%)	144 (100.00%)

The above table signifies preferences about searching the print resources over E-Resources.

From combining the scores of ‘Always’ (A) and ‘Frequently’ (F), it is discerned that the majority of faculty respondents i.e.48.61% (A= 6.94% + F = 41.67%) prefer E-Journals over E-books whereas 34.72% of respondents (A=11.11% + F = 23.61%) prefer Print resources over E-resources.

From the score of ‘Sometimes’, the data displays that majority of the faculty respondents i.e. 80.56% prefer E-books over E-journals followed by 45.83% of faculty respondents who prefer E-journals over E-books. It is also revealed that the 59.72% of faculty respondent’s occasionally doesn’t prefer any format.

From the scores of ‘Never’ and ‘Seldom’ options, it has been discerned that the 29.17% of the faculty respondents do not have any search preference while using N-LIST E-resources. Moreover, 2.08% of respondents have never ‘preferred e-journals over e-books’ whereas 23.61% of respondents rarely prefer ‘print resources over e-resources’ while browsing the N-LIST E-resources.

It has been deduced from the above table that a majority of the faculty respondents i.e. 80.56% sometimes prefer E-books over E-journals as well as Print resources. Thus it can be contemplated that 48.61% of faculty respondents fulfill their information needs and always preferred E-journals over E-books.

8.1 Preference using N-LIST E-resources by Students

Table-2: Student (Preference Using E-Resources)

Sr. No.	Frequency/ Preferences	Always	Frequently	Sometimes	Seldom N (%)	Never	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	
1.	Prefer Print Resource over E-resources	15 (10.56%)	44 (30.99%)	58 (40.85%)	25 (17.60%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)
2.	Prefer E-books over E journals	0 (0.00%)	48 (33.80%)	74 (52.11%)	16 (11.27%)	4 (2.82%)	142 (100.00%)
3.	Prefer E-journals over E-books	14 (9.86%)	43 (30.28%)	57 (40.14%)	20 (14.08%)	8 (5.64%)	142 (100.00%)
4.	No search Preference	0 (0.00%)	11 (7.75%)	110 (77.46%)	4 (2.82%)	17 (11.97%)	142 (100.00%)

The above table displays preferences about searching the print resources over E-Resources.

From combining the scores of the ‘Always’ (A) and ‘Frequently’ (F) options, it clearly indicates that the 41.55% (A= 10.56% + F = 30.99%) of the student respondents prefer print resources over E-resources followed by 40.14% (A=9.86% + F = 30.28%) of participants who prefer E-journals over E-books. Whereas 7.75% (A= 0.00% + F = 7.75%) of the respondents did not have any search preference.

From the scores of ‘Sometimes’ options, it was noticed that 40.85% of student preferprint resources over E-resources. While some of student respondents i.e. 52.11% prefer E-books over E-journals. Whereas majority of student respondents i.e. 77.46% don’t have any search preference.

From the scores of ‘Never’ and ‘Seldom’ options, it has been perceived that the 11.97% of the student respondents do not have any search preference while using N-LIST E-resources. Moreover, 5.64% of respondents have never ‘preferred e-journals over e-books’ whereas 17.60% of respondents rarely prefer ‘print resources over e-resources’ while browsing the N-LIST E-resources.

It can be inferred that the majority of student respondents i.e. 77.46% don't have any search preference, occasionally. While 41.55% of student respondents usually prefer print resources while sougning information.

8.2 Preference using N-LIST E-resources : Faculty Vs Student Users

From the above discussion, it can be deduced that the majority of faculty respondents i.e. 48.61% prefer E-Journals over E-books whereas 41.55% of student respondents usually prefer print resources over E-resources while seeking information from the N-LIST E-resources. As the Common belief, the e-resources is mostly preferred by the users and the e-resources can be easily accessed and convenient to use. But on the contrary, the student users prefer print resources over e-resources as they are getting conducive environment and support from the library.

9.0 Purpose for using N-LIST E-Resources:

Table-3: Faculty (Purpose For Using N-List E-Resources)

Sr. No.	Statement/Purpose	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Understand research trends & Remain Updated	19 (13.19%)	88 (61.11%)	33 (22.92%)	4 (2.78%)	0 (0.00%)	144 (100.00%)
2.	Seminars /conferences etc	9 (6.25%)	114 (79.17%)	15 (10.42%)	1 (0.69%)	5 (3.47%)	144 (100.00%)
3.	Writing research Projects	12 (8.33%)	79 (54.86%)	38 (26.40%)	1 (0.69%)	14 (9.72%)	144 (100.00%)
4.	Quality teaching aids	8 (5.56%)	71 (49.31%)	50 (34.72%)	12 (8.33%)	3 (2.08%)	144 (100.00%)
5.	For Writing Book/ Book Chapters	13 (9.03%)	68 (47.22%)	49 (34.03%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (9.72%)	144 (100.00%)
6.	Writing Research Paper/ articles	45 (31.25%)	49 (34.03%)	22 (15.28%)	14 (9.72%)	14 (9.72%)	144 (100.00%)
7.	Training Others	13 (9.03%)	49 (34.03%)	54 (37.50%)	15 (10.41%)	13 (9.03%)	144 (100.00%)

The above table helps in comprehending the various purposes of the faculty respondents for using the N-LIST E-resources.

From combining the scores of 'Agree' (A) and 'Strongly Agree'(SA), it can be analysed that 85.42% (A=79.17% + SA= 6.25%) of faculty respondents sought information for seminars/ conferences followed by 74.30% (A= 61.11% + SA = 13.19%) of respondents feels that it helps in understanding research trends and remain updated. 63.19% (A= 54.86%+SA= 8.33%) of respondents sought information for writing research projects and remain updated. While 56.25% (A= 47.22% + SA= 9.03%) of faculty respondents feel that N-LIST E-resources enable them for writing books/ book chapters.

From the scores of 'Disagree' and 'Strongly Disagree', it has been mentioned that the 9.72% of faculty respondents feels that N-LIST e-resources doesn't help them in writing research projects, book chapters and research articles. Moreover, 10.41% of respondents it does not help the faculty user in training others.

It was interjected from the above table that most of faculty respondents i.e. 85.42% sought information for conferences and seminars presentations followed by 74.30% of respondents who sought information in understanding research trends from the N-LIST E-resources. This reveals that the main purpose of the faculty respondents for using N-LIST E-resources is writing articles for conferences and seminars presentations. In contrast, **Akinola (2009)** obtained the different results from her study which revealed that majority of the

respondents (35.4%) from the University of Ibadan sought information to update knowledge. It was also found that the respondents also sought information for writing of papers or books, reading, and for preparing class lectures.

9.2 Purpose for Using N-LIST E-Resources

Table-4: Student (Purpose for Using N-LIST E-resources)

Sr. No.	Scale/ Purpose	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Preparation of Assignment	37 (26.06%)	76 (53.52%)	25 (17.62%)	4 (2.82%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)
2.	Preparation of Student Seminars/ Presentation	34 (23.94%)	95 (66.90%)	7 (4.93%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (4.23%)	142 (100.00%)
3.	Internship/ Classroom Projects	36 (25.35%)	74 (52.11%)	26 (18.31%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (4.23%)	142 (100.00%)
4.	Group Discussion	34 (23.94%)	62 (43.66%)	40 (28.17%)	2 (1.41%)	4 (2.82%)	142 (100.00%)
5.	Personal Notes	36 (25.35%)	60 (42.25%)	40 (28.17%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (4.23%)	142 (100.00%)
6.	Competitive Examinations	47 (33.10%)	69 (48.59%)	9 (6.33%)	11 (7.75%)	6 (4.23%)	142 (100.00%)
7.	Training Projects	52 (36.62%)	28 (19.72%)	44 (30.99%)	12 (8.44%)	6 (4.23%)	142 (100.00%)
8.	Market Survey etc	16 (11.27%)	0 (0.00%)	126 (88.73%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)
9.	Remain Updated	16 (11.27%)	0 (0.00%)	126 (88.73%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)
10.	Gaining Knowledge	16 (11.27%)	0 (0.00%)	126 (88.73%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)

The above table helps in comprehending the various purposes of the student respondents for using the N-LIST E-resources.

From combining the scores of 'Agree' (A) and 'Strongly Agree' (SA), it was analysed that 90.84% (A=66.90% + SA=23.94 %) of student respondents opted for fulfilling the purpose of preparation of Student seminars/ presentations followed by 81.69% (A=48.59% + SA= 33.10%) of student respondents sought information for preparation of competitive exams. However, 79.58% (A=53.52% + SA=26.86%) of student respondents feels that N-LIST E-resources helped in preparation of assignments given to them in their respective subjects. While 77.46% (A=52.11% + SA= 25.35%) of student respondents agree with the statement that these e-resources help them in preparing the internship projects or projects related to their area/ discipline. Some of the student respondents i.e. 67.60% (A=43.66% + SA= 23.94%) and 67.60% (A=42.25% + SA= 25.35%) sought information for group discussions and preparation of personal notes.

From the scores of 'Disagree' and 'Strongly Disagree', it has been noticed that the 4.23% of student respondents feels that N-LIST e-resources did nothelp them in preparation of seminars, personal notes and competitive examinations. Moreover, 8.44% of studentsrarely help them in training projects.

From the above table, it can be inferredthat 90.84% of student respondents sought information for of preparation of Seminars followed by 81.69% of respondents who retrieved information for preparation of competitive exams from the N-LIST E-resources.

9.3 Purpose for using N-LIST E-Resources: Faculty Vs Student Users

It was evident from the above table that most of faculty respondents i.e. 85.42% sought information for conferences and seminars presentations. On the contrary, the 90.84% of student respondents sought information for preparation of Student Seminars/ presentations followed by 81.69% of respondents who retrieved information for preparation of competitive exams from the N-LIST E-resources. It is understood that the N-LIST E-resources are helpful for fulfilling their academic pursuits.

10.0 Findings

1. A majority of the **faculty respondents** i.e. 48.61% of faculty respondents fulfill their information needs and always preferred **E-journals over E-books** while deriving information.
2. It has been revealed that faculty usually sought information for updating their research areas from the E-journals.
3. A majority of the **student respondents** i.e. 41.55% **usually preferred print resources** while deriving information whereas a majority of student respondents i.e. 77.46% sometimes did not have any search preference.
4. A majority of **faculty respondents** i.e. 85.42% sought information for **conferences and seminars presentations** followed by 74.30% of respondents who sought information in **understanding research trends** from the N-LIST E-resources.
5. On the contrary, the 90.84% of **student respondents** sought information for preparation of **Student Seminars/ presentations** followed by 81.69% of respondents who retrieved information for **preparation of competitive exams** from the N-LIST E-resources.
6. It is understood that the N-LIST E-resources were helpful for the respondents who sought information in understanding research trends.
7. It is found that the main purpose of the faculty respondents for using N-LIST E-resources were writing articles for conferences and seminars presentations whereas the student respondents sought information for seminars writings /presentations and for preparation of competitive exams.

11.0 suggestions and recommendations

The study at hand was focussed on the evaluation of usage of N-LIST E-resources in the Select Degree Colleges Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. The libraries should endeavour to launch a marketing plan to promote the usage of N-LIST E-resources and its awareness among the users through email alerts, text messages, social networking sites, whatsapp groups, blogs, and wikis etc. It is suggested that the subscription cost of N-LIST E-resources should be reduced to the same as earlier for the Non-aided colleges also.

Further the research in this regard will widen the criteria of the study and identify as to how the faculty and the student from the member colleges affiliated to other Universities explore the usage of the N-LIST E-resources. The authors feel that there is a need for appropriate and constant evaluation of this study in order to enhance insight into the usage analysis and the relevance of the information retrieved from the N-LIST E-resources.

12.0 References

1. Akinola, S.F. Information Seeking Behaviour of Lecturers in Faculties of Education in Obafemi Awolowo University, Heilfe and University of Ibadan. *Samaru Journal of Information Studies*, 2009; 9(2): p.30.
2. Bhardwaj, R. K., & Walia, P. K. Web Based Information Sources and Services: A Case Study of St. Stephen's College, University of Delhi. *Library Philosophy and Practice* .<http://www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/bhardwaj-walia.html>. 2012.
3. Chattwal, A. *Information Seeking Behaviour of Social Science Faculty: a study of Universities of Punjab, Haryana and Chandigarh*. (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis). Panjab University, Chandigarh (India). 2014.
4. Kumbar, D., Chikkamanju, & Kumar, G. K. (2013). Use of N-LIST E-Resources by the Faculty and Student of University of Mysore Constituent Degree Colleges: A Comparative Study. *National Seminar on Emerging Trends in ERMS in College Libraries*. ISBN: 978-93-83302-01-7.p.6.
5. Krejice, R.V., & Morgan, D.W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurements*, 30, 607-610.
6. Nikam, K., & Pramodini, B (2007). Use of E-Journals and Datasbases by the Academic Community of University of Mysore: A Survey. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*. 54(1): 19-22.

7. Proportionate Random Stratified Sampling.(2013). In Stattrek.com. Retrieved on May 18, 2013. <http://stattrek.com/statistics/resources.aspx>
8. Sethi, B., & Panda, K. C. (2012). Use of e-resources by life scientists: a case study of Sambalpur University, India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Paper 681. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/681>
9. Chikkanmanju & Kumbar, M. (2015). Use of Information Resources and Services by the Students of First Grade Colleges Affiliated to Tumkur University, Tumkur: A Comparative Study. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*, 3(2), 53-64.